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Abstract

Today, for the effective development of the food industry in Uzbekistan, it is important to develop effective economic and managerial decisions and ensure their implementation. The article developed a model of the relationship between the cost of gross production and the depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets. The ascending order of the case under study is shown by flattening the time series using the least squares method. The dynamics of the wage fund, depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets in the food industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014-2023 and forecast values for 2024-2027 have been determined.

Аннотация

Сегодня для эффективного развития пищевой промышленности в Узбекистане важна выработка эффективных экономических и управленческих решений и обеспечение их реализации. В статье разработана модель взаимосвязи между стоимостью валовой продукции и износом основных средств и нематериальных активов. Порядок возрастания исследуемого случая показан путем выравнивания временных рядов с использованием метода наименьших квадратов. Определена динамика фонда оплаты труда, амортизация основных средств и нематериальных активов в пищевой промышленности Республики Узбекистан в 2014-2023 годах и прогнозные значения на 2024-2027 годы.

Keywords: food industry, gross product, regional product, forecasting model, cost, wages, fixed assets, intangible assets, depreciation.

Ключевые слова: пищевая промышленность, валовой продукт, региональный продукт, модель прогнозирования, стоимость, заработная плата, основные средства, нематериальные активы, амортизация.

Introduction. Today, it is important to develop effective economic and management decisions and ensure their implementation in order to improve the activities of food industry enterprises in Uzbekistan. The modern management system requires the use of reliable methods and tools to determine the future state and scope of economic processes and events. Econometric analysis of the development of the food industry makes it possible to study the power of dependence of complex socio-economic phenomena by means of economic-mathematical methods, to determine their laws and to observe them through experience [8].

A large number of software products have been created that speed up the process of applying these methods and allow you to select a significant model of analysis.

In the conditions of global climate change and pandemic, it is necessary to determine the goals and objectives of future development in order to ensure the rapid development of economic sectors [9]. It is more effective to use forecasting methods in the implementation of the goals and tasks of the development of economic sectors, in determining the factors affecting them. Because forecasting is another stage of the process of regulating the economy or part of the development of the country's socio-economic development program.

Analysis of literature on the topic. We, Y. Abdullayev [1], M.V. Gracheva, YE.A. Tumanova [2], D. Rasulev [3], in order to effectively develop the food industry in Uzbekistan and the Tashkent region and to develop a model for evaluating and forecasting economic processes. We studied the scientific works of

scientists such as A. Ishnazarov [4], YE.G. Semyonova [5], S.A. Borodich [6]. They developed forecasting methods based on econometric analysis, that is, correlation-regression analysis, and worked on their improvement.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of statistical theory, classification and grouping of statistical observation materials, basis of variation indicators and dispersion analysis, statistical study of connections between social phenomena, economic indices and other issues are covered in the textbook "Statistical Theory" [1].

In the monograph "Matematicheskiye i instrumentalniye metodi v sovremennix ekonomicheskix issledovaniyax" modern research and development of theoretical and methodological rules in the field of analysis of economic processes and systems based on the use of economic and mathematical methods and tools, examines the mathematical apparatus of economic research, uses it to increase the effectiveness of decisions and offers placement of tools [2].

Basics of econometric modeling, information support of econometric models, double and multi-factor econometric analysis, evaluation of econometric models, timing decisions, econometric model in the form of a system of equations, practical econometric models, economic the essence of the use of econometric models in forecasting indicators [3].

In this tutorial, the concepts of econometrics, the basics of mathematical statistical methods, the multivariable regression model and the ways to eliminate the multicollinearity and autocorrelation

problems that appear in it, as well as the methods of creating forecast models and evaluating their accuracy are covered with examples. [4].

The book "Fundamentals of Econometric Analysis" focuses on building econometric models based on spatial data and time series [10]. Brief methodological rules, including basic concepts, definitions, and formulas are given. Examples of solving typical problems are considered.

Procedures, mathematical hardware and software tools for modeling econometric analysis problems are presented [5].

This manual presents the fundamentals of econometrics, economic processes and the main models and methods of analyzing indicators based on statistical data [6].

Research methodology. A model of the dependence of the gross product value on the payroll, fixed assets and intangible assets depreciation was developed. By smoothing the time series using the method of least squares, the order of growth of the studied condition is reflected [11]. Data for 2014-2023 were used to determine the efficiency of food industry enterprises, to determine the impact of resource consumption on the gross product.

Analysis and results. Today, for the sustainable development of economic sectors, scientists have developed a number of methods for planning and forecasting economic indicators in advance, using information that fully reflects their activity [12]. One of the more widely used methods in practice is the least squares method. The essence of this method is to reduce the sum of squared deviations between observed and calculated quantities [7, 54 pages]. The smaller the difference between the actual and estimated values, the more accurate the forecast calculated based on the regression equation. The theoretical analysis of the

essence of the studied situation, its change reflected in the time series, is the basis for choosing the curve. In some cases, row-level growth is considered. If the increase in output is observed in an arithmetic progression, then the leveling is in a straight line [13]. If the growth is in a geometric progression, then the smoothing is done using an exponential function. The formula of the method of least squares is as follows:

$$y_t = a_0 + a_1 * t \quad (1)$$

here: a_0 , a_1 are parameters of the equation;
 t is a time symbol.

Parameter a_1 is a regression coefficient that determines the direction of development. If $a_1 > 0$, the terms of the dynamic range increase uniformly, if $a_1 < 0$, they decrease [14].

By smoothing the time series using the method of least squares, it serves to reflect the order of growth of the studied condition. In the analytical view of the trend, time is taken as the independent variable, and the level of the series is taken as a function of this independent variable. The development of the condition depends not on how much time has passed, but on what factors have influenced its development, and in what direction it is developing rapidly. Development over time is the result of these factors [15].

In order to make a forecast, we construct a linear equation formula for each factor using Microsoft Excel. Initially, the salary fund for the Republic of Uzbekistan is forecast.

From the calculation results, the equation looked like this:

$$y_t = 264,3 + 200,8 * t_1$$

Based on the equation, the series can be continued, that is, t keeps increasing. We can see it in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. The dynamics of the wage fund in food industry enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2014-2023 and forecast values for 2024-2027, (million soums)²

In the same order, depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets and gross product value were also forecast and the following results were obtained (Figure 2): [16]

$$y_t = 93,5 + 112,7 * t_1$$

²Compiled by the author based on the data of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Figure 2. Dynamics of depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets in food industry enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2014-2023 and forecast values for 2024-2027, (million soums)³

To forecast the value of the gross product in the Republic of Uzbekistan, we use the results of the wage fund, depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets forecast. For this, the regression equation on the factors affecting the change in the value of the gross product is obtained, i.e. $y(x) = -17.3x_1 + 76.53x_2 + 7828.6$. The forecast result is shown in Table-1 below: [17]

The volume of production of consumer products by food industry enterprises in 2019 was 70776.6 billion. amounting to soums, this indicator is expected to

increase by 2.5 times by 2030. Also, the state of food production in 2019-2023 was studied, and in the forecast for 2024-2030, the production volume of food products will increase by 1.7 times, the production of wine-vodka products and beer will increase by almost 1.9 times, non-food - it is forecasted that the production volume of food products will increase by 3.0 times (Table-2) [18].

Table 1.

2014-2023 dynamics and 2024-2027 forecast values of the main economic indicators in food industry enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan³

Years	time t	Salary fund, million soums	Depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets, million soums	Gross product, billion soums
2014	1	361,88	245,10	16888,0
2015	2	705,67	343,14	18154,6
2016	3	890,01	421,37	26782,3
2017	4	1015,94	442,23	28194,7
2018	5	1137,85	535,10	31695,8
2019	6	2210,85	1006,18	43483,6
2020	7	1149,64	817,02	51647,7
2021	8	1870,7	995,1	51620,5
2022	9	2071,5	1107,8	56771,6
2023	10	2272,3	1220,5	61922,7
2024	11	2473,1	1333,2	67073,8
2025	12	2673,9	1445,9	72224,9
2026	13	2874,7	1558,6	77375,9
2027	14	3075,5	1671,3	82527,1

Table 2.

2019-2023 state of consumer goods production by food industry enterprises and forecast indicators for 2024-2030 (billion soums)⁴

Years	Total consumer products	Including		
		food products	wine-vodka products and beer	non-food products
2019	7076,6	24738,5	2504,4	43533,7
2020	78406,2	26328,4	2691,3	49386,5
2021	86413,4	27918,4	2882,6	55612,4
2022	94797,8	29508,3	3078,2	62211,3

³ Compiled by the author based on the data of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

⁴ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti huzuridagi Statistika agentligima'lumotlari asosida muallif tomonidan tuzilgan

2023	103559,7	31098,3	3278,1	69183,3
2024	112698,8	32688,2	3482,3	76528,3
2025	122215,5	34278,2	3690,9	84246,4
2026	132109,5	35868,1	3903,9	92337,5
2027	142380,9	37458,1	4121,2	100801,6
2028	153029,6	39048,0	4342,8	109638,8
2029	164055,8	40638,0	4568,8	118849,0
2030	175459,3	42227,9	4799,1	128432,3

If we pay attention to the dynamics of production of food consumer products by the industrial enterprises of our republic according to the indicators of the perspective for 2019-2030, bread and bakery products will increase by 1.49 times (148%), flour by 1.81 times (180.8%), cereal by 1.3 times (130.0%), pasta products by 1.61 times (160.6%), meat and meat products by 1.32 times (131.8%), including goods, food, fish products, canned goods by 1.45 times (145.1%), milk and milk products by 1.76 times (175.7%), vegetable oil production is expected to increase by 1.03 times (103.0%) [23]. Also, in the coming years, industrial enterprises are expected to increase the production volume of food products, including beef fat by 1.64 times (164), canned fruit and vegetables by 1.12 times (112), margarine products by 1.30 times (129.6%), sugar by 1.52 times (151.7%), natural tea by 1.68 times (168.3%), table salt, vodka, liqueur-vodka products will grow by 1.10 times (110.2%), and by 1.66 times (166.3%) [19].

Conclusions and suggestions

In conclusion, in order to effectively develop the activities of the food industry enterprises of our republic and provide the population with food products at the level of the established standards, it is necessary to achieve the above-mentioned perspective values [20].

In order to do this, it is necessary to analyze the data of the last three years on the basis of the above model of the wage fund, depreciation of fixed assets and intangible assets, as well as the volume of the gross product in each food industry production enterprise, and the future indicators for the next five years should be determined. [22] Also, it is important that the production of consumer goods is determined by the above calculation and its execution is controlled. This requires attracting innovative technologies, foreign and local investments to the food industry [21]. Attracting advanced innovative technologies and investments will, in turn, lead to an increase in the regional gross product and supply the population with quality food products.

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